

Supplementary Figures DHA and hypoxia and 3T3L1 adipocytes

Supplementary Figures

Suppl Figure 1. Cell Line : ZenBio 3T3-L1 Preadipocytes

Suppl Figure 2. Red Oil Staining

5X

10X

